

TAJIKISTAN'S WATER DIPLOMACY CONTRIBUTES TO GLOBAL SECURITY AND THE FUTURE OF THE REGION

IKROMOVA MAHINA NUMONOVNA

Senior teacher, Department of International Relations and Political Science International University of Tourism and Entrepreneurship of Tajikistan (IUTET).

SULTANOV MUKHAMMADALI ABDUKAKHKHOROVICH

1st year Master's degree in specialty 230101.00 – International Relations, Department of International Relations and Political Science, International University of Tourism and Entrepreneurship of Tajikistan (IUTET).

Abstract. *This article examines the Republic of Tajikistan's water diplomacy and its contribution to global security in the region and the world as a whole. Its primary objective, initiative, and solution to transboundary water issues are key. The article's relevance lies in the issue of drinking water shortages for the world's population, water for life, and the full-scale stability of societal development. It is important to remember that water issues are not solely the responsibility of one state; they involve colossal projects that are important and necessary for the development of countries and for ensuring the health and well-being of people. The scientific novelty of this study lies in the formulation and substantiation of forums and practical approaches to addressing water shortages for sustainable development, as well as the development of project actions to address these global challenges. Therefore, it should be noted that, based on this, the Republic of Tajikistan is actively pursuing water diplomacy and aims to play an important role in the international arena in resolving a number of water-related issues in the region. The analyzed research on Tajikistan's water diplomacy can be used to develop the stability of countries and the region in securing water resources.*

Key words: *global security, water diplomacy of Tajikistan, Central Asia, cooperation, regional projects, international organizations, climate problem, water and energy resources.*

ВОДНАЯ ДИПЛОМАТИЯ ТАДЖИКИСТАНА ВКЛАД В ГЛОБАЛЬНУЮ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬ И БУДУЩЕЕ РЕГИОНА

ИКРОМОВА МАХИНА НУМОНОВНА

Старший преподаватель, кафедры международных отношений и политологии Международного университета туризма и предпринимательство Таджикистана (МУТПТ)

СУЛТОНОВ МУХАММАДАЛИ АБДУКАХХОРОВИЧ

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Аннотация. *Статья посвящена вопросу водной дипломатии Республики Таджикистан вклад в глобальную безопасность региона и мира в целом. Основная задача, инициатива и решение водных проблем в трансграничных вопросах. Актуальность статьи заключается в том, что вопрос нехватки питьевой воды для населения мира, вода для жизни для полномасштабной стабильности развития общества. Необходимо учитывать, что водная проблематика, это не только задача одного государства, это колоссальные проекты, которые важны и необходимы для развития стран, для обеспечения здоровья и благополучия людей. Научная новизна исследования заключается в постановке и обосновании форумов и*

ОФ "Международный научно-исследовательский центр "Endless Light in Science"

практических подходов к содержанию проблем нехватки воды для устойчивого развития, а также в разработке проектных действий по решению этих глобальных проблем. Следовательно, нужно отметить, что, исходя из этого, Республика Таджикистан активно реализует водную дипломатию, ставит перед собой цель играть важную роль на международной арене в деле разрешения ряд проблем, связанных с водной проблематикой в регионе. Анализировано исследования водной дипломатии Таджикистана могут быть использованы для развития стабильности стран и региона по обеспечению водных ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: *глобальная безопасность, водная дипломатия Таджикистана, Центральная Азия, сотрудничество, проекты региона, международные организации, климатическая проблема, водно-энергетические ресурсы.*

Water, as a critical resource for sustainable development is included in many development documents and strategies at the global, regional and national levels. A key aspect of these efforts has been the inclusion of objectives for addressing various aspects of water issues in the Sustainable Development Goals. This was facilitated by the enormous work and efforts of various stakeholders.

In the context of Central Asia, where water flow is primarily generated in the two upstream countries and the lion's share is used by downstream countries, interstate water cooperation is key not only to addressing water issues and socioeconomic development, but also to peace, stability and security.

Moreover, today the impact of challenges such as climate change and population growth in the region is becoming more obvious and pronounced. For example, while per capita water availability in the region was 8,400 m³/year in the 1960s, today this figure has decreased fourfold, to 2,100 m³/year. This is almost eight times higher than global levels.

Meanwhile, the region's population growth rate is among the highest in the world—over 2% per year—and freshwater resources are depleting at an ever-increasing rate.

According to expert estimates, Central Asia's glaciers, the main source of the region's rivers, are shrinking at an average rate of 0.6–0.8% per year in terms of glaciated area and approximately 0.1% in terms of ice volume. This requires urgent measures to adapt to drastic climate change and ensure sustainable water resource management in the region. This, in turn, can only be achieved through coordinated action by all countries based on well-established regional cooperation, a balanced consideration of their interests, improved institutional and legal frameworks, and a significant increase in infrastructure investment.

Along with the above, there are numerous other problems and challenges that exacerbate the current situation and undermine countries' efforts to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals. Clearly, these trends will continue in the coming decades, and humanity must take all necessary measures and actions to address them.

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the Addis Ababa Action Agenda of the Third International Conference on Financing for Development, the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030, and the Paris Agreement on Climate Change have already laid a solid foundation for further advancing water issues at various levels. However, successful resolution requires political will, the mobilization of all stakeholders and adequate approaches and tools.

Tajikistan has made and continues to make a significant contribution to this process. At our initiative, the General Assembly adopted seven resolutions on water issues between 2000 and 2016, including the declaration of 2003 as the International Year of Freshwater, 2005-2015 as the International Decade for Action, "Water for Life," 2013 as the International Year of Water Cooperation and 2018-2028 as the International Decade for Action, "Water for Sustainable Development," which deserve special attention. During this period, Tajikistan has repeatedly served as a platform for discussions on water issues at the global level.

Over the past two decades, the Republic of Tajikistan has become a recognized international center for advancing water and climate issues. Emomali Rahmon, the President of the Republic of Tajikistan and Leader of the Nation, played a fundamental role in this process. Under his leadership,

water issues, glacier conservation, and sustainable environmental management have become a strategic priority for the state and a crucial element of national security.

Thanks to strategic vision and systemic diplomacy, the country has managed to elevate water and climate issues to the level of global challenges, shaping new approaches to ensuring sustainable development, energy and environmental security. Tajikistan has become one of the states that has successfully united regional challenges and the interests of the international community around the water agenda, stimulating expert discussions and decision-making within the UN. In the concept of foreign policy of the Republic of Tajikistan, in the section on water cooperation diplomacy, it is noted that “due to population growth, expansion of agricultural land, irrational use of water resources, climate change and environmental problems, issues of shortage of drinking water, use of large and small transboundary rivers and other issues related to water are becoming factors that have a significant impact on international relations.” [3]

In accordance with the Charter of the United Nations (UN) and international law, the Republic of Tajikistan has the full right to use its natural resources, including water, to ensure sustainable development and decent living conditions for its people. The Republic of Tajikistan exercises this right with regard to water use based on regional interests, based on the principles of good neighborliness, respect, and genuine consideration of mutual interests, dialogue and cooperation in resolving existing problems. As a state located upstream and the main source of water resources in Central Asia, it will under no circumstances create obstacles to the region's water supply. Taking this principled position into account, one of the priority objectives of Tajikistan's foreign policy is to promote the country's energy independence and implement measures to address these challenges in the spirit of equal regional partnership and cooperation. [5]

Tajikistan has elevated the concept of water diplomacy to a practical level and truly refined it. The idea of water diplomacy differs from its traditional or classical understanding and requires the introduction of new negotiation techniques that can contribute to the successful resolution of conflicts over the management and use of transnational river water resources. Tajikistan's initiatives contribute to the creation of a stable basis for coordinating and stimulating efforts to address water management issues. Tajikistan's initiatives will help attract greater and more comprehensive attention to the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals and their targets. The aforementioned water-related challenges have created a new strategic goal for humanity and the provision of a dignified life for people. [17]

According to UN agencies, approximately 900 million people today lack safe drinking water, and approximately 3 billion people lack access to modern sanitation. Food insecurity affects up to one-third of the world's population. By 2030, almost half the world's population could be living in regions with high levels of water stress. The situation is further complicated by the lack of coordination between states that share transboundary water basins. These basins account for 45% of the world's land mass and are home to residents of 145 countries. Any instability in the water and energy balance could lead to international tensions. For the states of Central Asia, where more than half of the Aral Sea Basin's runoff originates in Tajikistan, these challenges are particularly pressing. It was the President of the Republic of Tajikistan, Emomali Rahmon, who authored and initiated key decisions adopted by the UN General Assembly that influenced global understanding of water and climate issues.

These initiatives played a significant role in shaping the global water agenda, raising awareness of the importance of preserving glaciers – a critical source of water for Asia, Europe, and other regions.

The Dushanbe Water Process is a recognized global platform. Since 2018, Tajikistan has been hosting the Dushanbe Water Process, an international mechanism for exchanging best practices and developing solutions on water issues. It has become one of the target platforms in preparation for the Second UN Water Conference, held in New York in 2023 in co-hosted by the Kingdom of the Netherlands. At the 2023 conference, 700 initiatives were announced, over 10,000 participants represented and the water and climate agenda entered a new phase of practical implementation. The

key thesis of the President of the Republic of Tajikistan was also voiced there: “Water should be considered a factor of peace, cooperation and sustainable development.”

Three main ways to address the water issue in Central Asia:

➤ Cooperation between countries. One of the key factors in overcoming the water issue in Central Asia is cooperation between the countries of the region. Central Asian water resources, such as the Amu Darya and Syr-Darya rivers, are transboundary and require joint management. Countries need to develop and implement coordinated action plans based on the principles of equitable and efficient use of water resources. However, regional structures dealing with water issues face limited capacity and a lack of mutual trust between stakeholders.

➤ Improving water use efficiency. Countries in the region should make efforts to improve the efficiency of irrigation systems and implement advanced technologies and water management practices. This may include modernizing irrigation systems, using drip irrigation, and introducing modern agricultural practices that will reduce water loss and increase crop yields. Furthermore, it is important to develop infrastructure for rainwater collection and storage, as well as for industrial and domestic use.

➤ Developing alternative water sources could play a significant role in addressing the water crisis in Central Asia. One possible avenue is the development of groundwater resources and the use of seawater. Countries in the region could also explore opportunities for cooperation on transboundary water projects.

Glaciers are a strategic resource for Tajikistan and the region, helping to address a number of environmental issues. Tajikistan has over 11,000 square kilometers of glaciers—approximately 8% of the country's territory—accumulating 845 cubic kilometers of freshwater. Glaciers ensure a stable supply of the region's main rivers: Amu Darya, Vakhsh, Panj and Syr-Darya. Climate change is accelerating their melting, posing risks.

In this regard, President Emomali Rahmon was the first to raise the issue of glacier melting at the UN level, presenting a holistic vision for preserving mountain glaciers as a factor in global security.

The introduction of the International Year of Glacier Conservation (2025) is Tajikistan's response to the need to monitor and prevent these threats.

Water resources in Tajikistan: scientific assessment and river potential are crucial for the development of the region as a whole. There are 25,227 rivers and streams in the country, contributing an annual flow of 64 cubic kilometers of water—55% of the annual resources of the Aral Sea basin. Lakes and Reservoirs Tajikistan has over 2,300 lakes (705 km²), with a total storage capacity of 46.3 km³, including 20 km³ of freshwater. Eleven large reservoirs operate with a total usable volume of 7.5 km³. Groundwater renewable resources are estimated at 18.7 km³ per year, of which 2.8 km³ are available for use. These data underscore the country's exceptional role as the natural "water heart" of Central Asia.

Tajikistan demonstrates that water issues can serve as a tool for cooperation rather than confrontation. The country's proposed model combines. This approach is considered by experts as a foundation for preventing potential conflicts, given that there are over 200 disputed transboundary rivers worldwide.

In recent years, Tajikistan, under the leadership of President Emomali Rahmon, has become a key architect of the global water and climate agenda. Thanks to the head of state's initiative, Water Diplomacy has become a fully-fledged component of the country's international policy, offering the world new ways to address water shortages, climate risks and the conservation of natural resources. The country is not only demonstrating political will but also offering tools that will ensure water security for future generations.

In the face of population growth, climate change and resource scarcity, Tajikistan's experience is becoming a model for countries seeking to ensure sustainability and harmony between people and nature.

The outcome document of the Rio+20 UN International Conference on Sustainable Development, "The Future We Want," identified water as the foundation for achieving sustainable development. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development included water as a separate SDG goal. As a logical extension of these ideas, the Republic of Tajikistan proposed declaring the period 2018-2028 the International Decade for Action, "Water for Sustainable Development," a proposal supported by all UN member states. The Decade will serve as an important platform for political dialogue, the exchange of information and experience, and a crucial tool for promoting the achievement of internationally agreed water-related goals and targets, including those contained in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

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